

THE NEED FOR A SIMPLIFIED APPROACH TO TEACHING LINGUISTICS

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Annotation. *The text provides a comprehensive exploration of text linguistics, emphasizing its role in language teaching and translation studies. Key challenges in teaching text linguistics are identified, including its complexity and resource demands. The text proposes solutions such as practical methodologies and the use of technology. Empirical research underscores the benefits of text analysis in translation education, particularly in addressing deficiencies in traditional methods. The discussion highlights the evolution of text linguistics, from sentence-level analysis to embracing corpus-based approaches and social-pragmatic considerations.*

Keywords. *Text linguistics, text analysis, translation studies, language teaching, corpus linguistics, pragmatics, semiotics, cohesion and coherence, translator training, pedagogy*

Аннотация. *Текст представляет собой всестороннее исследование текстовой лингвистики, подчеркивая ее роль в преподавании языка и переводе. Выявлены ключевые проблемы обучения текстовой лингвистике, включая ее сложность и ресурсозатратность. В тексте предлагаются решения, такие как практические методики и использование технологий. Эмпирические исследования подчеркивают преимущества анализа текстов в образовательных программах по переводу, особенно при устранении недостатков традиционных методов. Обсуждение освещает*

эволюцию текстовой лингвистики от анализа на уровне предложений до использования корпусного подхода и социально-прагматических аспектов.

Ключевые слова. *Текстовая лингвистика, анализ текста, переводоведение, преподавание языков, корпусная лингвистика, прагматика, семиотика, когезия и когерентность, обучение переводчиков, педагогика.*

Annotatsiya: Matn lingvistikasi haqida keng qamrovli tadqiqot taqdim etilgan bo‘lib, uning til o‘qitish va tarjima tadqiqotlaridagi roli alohida ta’kidlanadi. Matn lingvistikasi o‘qitishdagi asosiy muammolar, jumladan, uning murakkabligi va resurs talab qilishi aniqlangan. Matnda amaliy metodikalar va texnologiyalardan foydalanish kabi yechimlar taklif etiladi. Empirik tadqiqotlar matn tahlilining tarjima ta’limida, ayniqsa, an’anaviy usullarning kamchiliklarini bartaraf etishda foydali ekanligini ta’kidlaydi. Munozarada matn lingvistikasi taraqqiyoti, jumla darajasidagi tahlildan boshlab, korpusga asoslangan yondashuv va ijtimoiy-pragmatik jihatlarni qamrab olishgacha bo‘lgan evolyutsiya ko‘rsatiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar. *Matn lingvistikasi, matn tahlili, tarjimashunoslik, til o‘qitish, korpus lingvistikasi, pragmatika, semiotika, bog‘lanish va izchillik, tarjimonlarni o‘qitish, pedagogika.*

INTRODUCTION

Text linguistics is an essential field within linguistics that examines the structure and communicative function of texts. Its significance extends to language teaching, where it aids in understanding how texts are constructed and how meaning is conveyed. However, the complexity of the subject presents challenges for both learners and educators, necessitating simplified and practical approaches. This paper explores these challenges and proposes solutions, including the integration of text analysis in translator training programs to enhance translation quality. Furthermore, there is a need for simplification because text analysis can be time-consuming and resource-intensive. Teachers may feel overwhelmed by the amount of time required to analyze texts thoroughly and may struggle to fit this

into their curriculum. Therefore, there is a need for an approach that simplifies this process without sacrificing its effectiveness.¹

METHODOLOGY

The study investigated the impact of text-linguistic instruction on translation performance among Iranian university students. Two groups alternated between a text-linguistic course and traditional translation training, with pre-tests, mid-tests, and post-tests evaluating their progress. Independent raters assessed the translations based on structural, textual, and contextual considerations. The study aimed to determine whether systematic text analysis improves decision-making in translation compared to traditional methods. To address these issues, practical teaching approaches are recommended, such as using authentic texts for step-by-step analysis, employing graphic organizers to identify textual features, and integrating technology like text analysis software for immediate feedback. The growing focus on corpus linguistics has also advanced understanding by providing empirical insights into linguistic patterns, moving beyond the limitations of earlier sentence-based approaches. First, the semantic and pragmatic constraints set aside by formalist models are effectively restored and placed on a more realistic basis than ever before. Second, we see that the appropriate unit for analysis is not the morpheme, word, or phrase but the ‘co-text’, the utterance environment, of variable lengths, in which words or phrases tend to appear together. And third, we no longer need to cut up linguistics into tidy ‘levels’ or ‘components’ for separate analysis and description; even the staid division between grammar and lexicon proves to be merely two complementary points of view upon the same phenomena².

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The findings revealed that students exposed to text-linguistic training demonstrated significant improvement in translation quality, particularly in areas

¹ "Text Structure and Coherence" by T.A. van Dijk (1977.p-47

² N.Schneider & S.Kiesling. Textual Features and Genre Analysis in Business Communication Teaching,2010.-P.247

such as register, pragmatics, and semiotics. In contrast, the traditional method primarily enhanced structural aspects but lacked effectiveness in teaching contextual and functional considerations. These results underscore the necessity of systematic text analysis as part of translator training, providing students with criteria to analyze texts effectively and make informed decisions during translation. Studies suggest that incorporating text linguistics into teaching improves students' ability to translate texts effectively by equipping them with analytical tools to consider factors like register, pragmatics, and semiotics. Despite the traditional focus on grammar and structure, systematic text analysis is essential to enhance decision-making in translation. Research conducted among Iranian university students demonstrated the positive impact of a text-linguistic course on translation quality, confirming the need for organized approaches in translator training programs.

CONCLUSION

Simplified approaches to teaching text linguistics are crucial for overcoming the challenges faced by students and educators. Incorporating practical methodologies and systematic text analysis not only enhances comprehension but also equips learners with the tools to analyze and produce meaningful translations. The findings highlight the importance of integrating text-linguistic principles into educational curricula to improve translation quality and foster a deeper understanding of language. For van Dijk, a text was “the abstract theoretical construct underlying discourse”; or “a sentence sequence with a macro-structure”, i.e. a “global structure of meaning”. For Hartmann, the text was a “finite ordered set of textually complicated partial signs of various sorts and functions” and hence “the linguistically significant Original sign of language”³.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. "Text Structure and Coherence" by T.A. van Dijk (1977.p-47

³ M. McCarthy. Discourse Analysis for Language Teachers. 1991.-P.69

2. N.Schneider & S.Kiesling. Textual Features and Genre Analysis in Business Communication Teaching.2010.-P.247
3. M. McCarthy. Discourse Analysis for Language Teachers. 1991.-P.69